

VALUE ASPECTS OF THE SAFE EXISTENCE OF SOCIAL SYSTEMS IN AN UNSTABLE WORLD

Oleg Danilyan,*

odana@i.ua

Olexander Dzoban,**

a_dzeban@ukr.net

Yurii Kalynovskyi,***

kalina_uu@ukr.net

Mykola Saltanov****

mykola.saltanov@karazin.ua

Abstract: *The paper analyzes the axiological aspects of the safe existence of society in conditions of global instability. The authors defined the essence of social solidarity as a factor of increasing stability in social systems. The importance of social justice for reducing the level of conflict in the existence of modern societies has been proven. The institutional importance of democracy and democratic values for the safe development of social systems is substantiated.*

Keywords: *social system, human rights and freedoms, global instability, solidarity, justice, democratic values.*

Introduction

At the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century, "tectonic shifts" began to occur in the existing world order, which led to increased

* **Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Philosophy of Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Kharkiv, Ukraine.**

** **Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor, Professor Philosophy Department Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Kharkiv, Ukraine.**

*** **Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor, Professor Philosophy Department Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Kharkiv, Ukraine.**

**** **PhD. in Philosophy, Associate Professor of Philosophy Department, Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Kharkiv, Ukraine.**

instability both in certain regions of our planet and in the world as a whole. Global transformations have concerned all spheres of life of modern societies: economic, social, political, spiritual and valuable, communicative and informational etc. Global changes, on the one hand, created new opportunities for states and communities, and on the other hand, provoked the strengthening of crisis phenomena at various levels, intensified the struggle for spheres of influence in the world, and actualized the problem of preserving the homeostasis of social systems. In connection with the above, the need to develop the latest strategies for the safe existence of states and societies in conditions of global turbulence has significantly increased. Such strategies, in our opinion, should be based on certain value-oriented points, that reflect the specifics of national interests and priorities of a particular society. Despite such specificity, a number of basic axiologyemes can be distinguished, which form the basis for the creation of national programs of safe development during the increase of global instability. Such value orientations and priorities are peace, stability of the socio-economic system, social justice, social solidarity, mutually beneficial cooperation on a regional and global level, democracy, human rights and freedoms, preservation of the national identity of peoples, overcoming the ecological crisis and preventing man-made disasters, etc. In this paper, we plan to analyze only some of the above-mentioned values and axiological priorities, leaving consideration of others for further research. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to define and reveal the value guidelines for the safe existence of social systems in conditions of increased global instability.

Methodology

The methodological basis of our research is a complex of general scientific, philosophical, and philosophical-legal approaches and methods, which provided a comprehensive consideration of the problem of value aspects of the safe existence of social systems in a turbulent world. In particular, the dialectical method made it possible to trace the evolution of the value content of the concept of "security of the social system", and the synergistic method - to ground the role of values in self-organizing processes in social entities in order to maintain their stability.

The structural-functional method in combination with the normative-analytical method became the basis for identifying the level of influence of social justice and social solidarity, as value and legal phenomena, on the stability of the existence of democratic systems. With the help of the concretization method, the institutional and axiological significance of human rights and freedoms for the preservation of social stability was substantiated. In this regard, relying on methods of analysis and synthesis, the merits and demerits of democratic political and legal systems are outlined and their potential for maintaining social stability is analyzed.

Instead, the methods of classification and systematization contributed to the detecting and generalization of various theoretical and methodological positions regarding the understanding of values in the context of the safe existence of social entities in an unstable world, as well as the substantiation of indicators of social justice and forms of social solidarity.

Literature review

The problem of the safe existence of social systems in the axiological dimension was reflected in the scientific publications of researchers from various branches of knowledge. Referring to the history of the issue, we emphasize that this problem was analyzed in the books of the philosophical classics, in particular in the works of Charles Louis Montesquieu¹, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel² others. For instance Charles Louis Montesquieu emphasized the need for democratization of political power and social relations for the prosperity of the country, and Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel substantiated the determining role of the state in ensuring the stability of the social organism. In its turn, contemporary scientists V. Pivovar, S. Drachuk reflects on the relationship and essential characteristics of the concepts of "security" and "danger" in the context of increased global competition³.

In its turn, the authors of the research "Modern Ontology: Reflection of the Continuity of Cyberspace and Virtual Reality" analyze the conflictual aspects of the interaction of social and virtual spaces, defining the value difference of these worlds as one of the reasons for the instability of human existence in society⁴. In accordance with the above-mentioned logic O. Petryshyn and O. Gilyaka, emphasize that the results of digitization of many branches of life require the understanding and adequate formulation of the legal mechanism for the regulation, implementation, and protection of already existing and new human rights for the purpose of sustainable socio-economic development, ensuring the implementation and protection of constitutional human rights and civil rights and freedom. This research focuses on new rights, such as the right to anonymity, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to digital education and access to digital knowledge; rights related to the protection of genetic information; the right to participate in the circulation of property in the digital sphere⁵.

¹ C.-L. Montesquieu, *On the spirit of laws*. Moscow: Thought, 1999.

² W.V.G. Hegel, *Phenomenology of spirit* / trans. with Germ. P. Taraschuk, science. ed. trans. Y. Kushakov. Kyiv: Osnovy, 2004.

³ V. Pivovar, & S. Drachuk, *Philosophical problems of security as a methodological basis for ensuring the security of the stock market*. Legal informatics, 2007, 2(14), p. 77-82.

⁴ A. Hetman, O. Danilyan, O. Dzoban, & Y. Kalynovskyi, *Modern ontology: reflection on the continuity of cyberspace and virtual reality*. Revista de Filosofía, 2022, Vol. 39, Iss. 102, p. 78-94.

⁵ O. Petryshyn, & O. Hyliaka, *Human rights in the digital age: Challenges, threats and prospects*. Journal of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, 2021, 28(1), p. 15-23. doi:10.37635/jnalsu.28(1).2021.15-23.

The theme of the crisis of sociality, spirit and values is continued in the work of Y. Meliakova and coauthors. For a late capitalism autonomous individual, his or her corporeal and mental self-exploitation is considered as an effective integrative tactics. Performative utterances are the attempts to compensate for the deficient and limited online existence in the unfavourable conditions of the digital environment on the whole and quarantine, in particular. That way, purely virtual corporeal self-realisation, dominating these days, implicitly forces a vulnerable human to seek performative forms of self-realisation, self-defence and self-preservation⁶.

On the other hand, in the research work of G. Simmel⁷ and Z. Bauman⁸ revealed the role of social solidarity as a factor in the stable existence of society. The consolidating function of social solidarity is analyzed as well by O. Osipova⁹ and O. Palagniuk¹⁰, interpreting it as a manifestation of social self-organization, which has a dynamic character.

Researching social justice as a value basis for the security of social systems, we relied on the scientific works of A. Grynenko¹¹, L. Kravchenko¹², J. Rawls¹³, V. Studinsky¹⁴, N. Fedin¹⁵ and others. Scientific researches of S. Kosinov¹⁶, A. Kudryachenko¹⁷, T. Popovich¹⁸, A. Sen contributed to the justification of the idea of the value of democracy for progressive and safe

⁶ Y. Meliakova, I. Kovalenko, E. Kalnytskyi, & H. Kovalenko, *Performativity and self-exploitation: body significance in late capitalist era*. Cogito, 2021, Vol. 13, Iss. 4, p. 16.

⁷ H. Simmel, *Man as enemy*. Sociological journal, 1994, 2, p. 114-119.

⁸ Z. Bauman, *Postmodern ethics* / Trans. from English R. Zimovets, O. Yudin, D. Korol. Kyiv: Port-Royal, 2006.

⁹ E.V. Osipova, *Mechanical and organic solidarity*. Russian sociological encyclopedia. Moscow: NORMA-INFRA, 1999.

¹⁰ O.V. Palahniuk, *Socio-psychological aspects of social solidarity in the conditions of social transformations: an attempt at conceptualization*. Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University, 2022, 1, p. 67-76.

¹¹ A.M. Grynenko, *Social justice as a key principle in the implementation of the social policy of the state*. Scientific works of Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University of complex "Kyiv-Mohyla Academy". Ser.: Pedagogy, 2009, 112 (99), p. 104-107.

¹² L.V. Kravchenko, *Justice as a choice*. Kyiv: Molod, 1998.

¹³ J. Rawls, *Theory of justice*. Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk University Publishing House, 1995.

¹⁴ V. Studinsky, *The issue of social justice in the context of social policy*. Ukraine: aspects of Labor, 2009, 1, p. 13-16.

¹⁵ N.V. Fedina, *The concept of social justice in the theory of the state and law*. Legal novels, 2018, 4, p. 66-72.

¹⁶ S. Kosinov, *Democratic principles and values in the organization of public power*. Bulletin of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, 2013, 3 (74), p. 128-134.

¹⁷ A. Kudryachenko, *Fundamental democratic values and their impact on the development of civil society in European countries*. Viche, 2015, 2. URL: <https://veche.kiev.ua/journal/4541/> (access date: 07/10/2022).

¹⁸ T.P. Popovych, *Legal model of a modern democratic state*. Comparative and analytical law, 2016, 1, p. 65-68.

development of social entities. A number of scientists define human rights and freedoms as the core value of democracy in the axiological dimension, such scientists as V. Sokurenko¹⁹ and V. Tykhyi²⁰.

Results and Discussion

Under the influence of global turbulence, the very philosophy of safe existence is gradually changing, which involves strengthening the role of spirituality (spiritual security) and strengthening information security in the life of any community and humanity as a whole. For a comprehensive research of the issue of the safe existence of social systems in the axiological dimension during the intensification of global confrontation, let's briefly dwell on the consideration of the conceptual dichotomy "security" and "danger".

Revealing the philosophical aspects of security as a social phenomenon, it should emphasize that the concept of security and awareness of its necessity is manifested both on the sensory and rational levels. Premonitions, negative emotions, a sense of danger, a sense of self-defense with the subsequent conscious formation of a defense system are a manifestation of the richness of human being's nature, the inexhaustibility of human qualities. Security is a dynamic process that depends not only on the state and level of development of this or that system, but on the richness of human being's nature, on its psychology, feelings, moods, state of culture and civilization. Therefore, it is correct to pose the problem of identifying and revealing the essential characteristics of security as a social phenomenon. These should include self-sufficiency, self-preservation, security, stability of existence, protection from threats, guarantee, etc. In practical activities (in the sphere of political, economic, legal, cultural), this manifests itself in a state of protection from threats, increasing the potential for secure existence, strengthening reliability, improving the protection system, creating security guarantees for the development of the social system. Security is not an abstract phenomenon detached from concrete living conditions. This concept has and manifests its specific meaning based on specific circumstances, situations, social conditions as well. It acts as a need for human existence in general, as a need for the existence of a person, nation, state in particular, because its functioning is connected with the satisfaction of the most important need of human being and society - security of existence. Security is associated with the very possibility of life,

¹⁹ V.V. Sokurenko, *Human rights as a fundamental value*. National and international mechanisms for the protection of human rights: theses add. All-Ukrainian round table (Kharkiv, April 20, 2016) / Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, Kharkiv. national University of Internal Affairs affairs Kharkiv: Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, 2016, p. 7-9.

²⁰ V.P. Tikhii, *Human security is the main object of Ukraine's national security*. Spirituality of Person: methodology, theory and practice, 2017, 4, p. 323-329.

its preservation and protection from threats, it is understood as a value and criterion of development, which is connected with the awareness of a complex and systematic approach to security problems²¹.

At the same time, it should be emphasized that a significant increase in global and social turbulence determines the revision of the paradigm of safe existence, since new challenges and threats are no longer typical, and the protection system for their leveling is not developed in social systems at the proper level. In its turn, the system of values also undergoes changes: their content, ranking in public consciousness, implementation features, etc.

Scientists prove that during periods of crisis, when the basic value orientations of development change, the process of forming a new ideology of safe development on a new value basis usually begins, thanks to the inclusion of natural and artificial mechanisms of "social energy" regulation. In the conditions of an unstable state, there is a need to strengthen control over probable changes, since the actions of certain innovations can be useful with appropriate socio-cultural preparation, but can also cause various social dangers and threats. For instance, today the danger caused by globalization processes is that external borrowings, without their critical rethinking, are applied directly for social life under the guise of proven effective social means, which with the help of information technologies begin to "penetrate" and destroy the defensive reaction of traditional culture, mimicking allegedly under the already familiar interior of activity due to mass replication and endless repetition. Therefore, taking into account the needs of safe development, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that certain innovative changes contribute, first of all, to the consolidation of society, to the benefit of one's society. Identifying yourself with someone or something is the most convenient form of achieving a stable safe state, that is, self-preservation based on self-determination²².

Summarizing the reasons for the emergence and strengthening of social instability in the modern world, scientists emphasize that these are socio-economic and political crises, unsuccessful attempts to reform political-legal and economic systems, asynchrony of political and economic transformations, destructive external influence on social processes in a certain state²³.

In general, the problem of preserving the stability of social systems in the value dimension is not new. For instance Charles Louis Montesquieu developed the idea of the need, in the interests of state and public security,

²¹ V. Pivovarov, & S. Drachuk, *Philosophical problems of security as a methodological basis for ensuring the security of the stock market*. Legal informatics, 2007, 2(14), p. 78.

²² Y. Kysil, *Principles of social security formation in multicultural societies*. Political management, 2009, 2, p. 129-130.

²³ O. Danilyan, O. Dzoban, & Y. Kalynovskyi, *Social instability as a global trend of the modern world*. Cogito, 2022, Vol. 14, 3. p. 155.

to separate the three branches of government. In addition, he argued that liberal-humanist values and principles of a stable social system (condemnation of despotism, defense of civil and personal freedom, religious tolerance, political moderation, gradual change) are necessary and sufficient conditions for preserving and maintaining public security²⁴.

Instead, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel in his scientific investigations revealed the worldview and philosophical aspects of the human security, state and society. From his point of view, the main role in ensuring social and individual security is played by the state, because it is thanks to the state that the habit and conditions of a safe existence are formed in a person, which becomes his second nature. Researching the essence of the security problem, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel draws the following conclusion - the individual security guarantees the safety of society, that is, in fact, we are talking about the so-called integral security and safety, which the state must ensure. Refusal of the state from this function inevitably leads to the degradation of the totality of all social relations, the destruction of the social order. A significant decrease in the level of moral, legal, and cultural restrictions promotes the manifestation of selfishness, instincts, and violence. This is the root cause of the entire spectrum of dangers and threats to the existence of the individual, social groups, the state, civilization and humanity as a whole²⁵.

Nowadays, various methods are used to determine the stability of social systems and the parameters of their safe existence, which take into account a number of indicators, including spiritual-value, mental-cultural, worldview.

At the same time, according to experts, there is no generally accepted scientifically based quantitative indicator (index) in the world that would objectively measure the general state of national security. However, many countries of the world and international organizations quite widely use a variety of methods that allow indirectly, through the analysis of quantitative indicators of individual aspects of the socio-political, economic, socio-cultural, ecological and other life of the country, to arrive at a general assessment of the state of ensuring the national security of both an individual country and region as a whole. Such methods, the analysis of indicators (indices) of which in aggregate allows to reach a first approximation to a more or less objective assessment of the general state of national security, should include:

– The Sustainable Society Index (SSI) is a combined indicator of the Sustainable Society Foundation, which measures the achievements of countries in terms of the sustainability of social development.

²⁴ L.V. Kalashnikova, *Socio-philosophical origins of the formation of the concept of security in protosociology*. Grani, 2016, 9, p. 10.

²⁵ W.V.G. Hegel, *Phenomenology of spirit* / trans. with Germ. P. Taraschuk, science. ed. trans. Y. Kushakov. Kyiv: Osnovy, 2004, p. 42.

– Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) is a technique, the indicators of which can be used to assess the general state of each individual country in the world in the branch of national security. Within the framework of the project initiated by the World Bank (WB) in 1996, aggregate and individual indicators of the success of governance in individual countries of the world are presented according to six key management ratings (indices). Aggregate WGI indicators combine the views of a large number of respondents from more than 30 organizations, institutions and experts and use more than 40 data sources, covering almost 200 countries and have been updated annually since 2002²⁶.

Let's dwell in more detail on the value parameters of the safe existence of social systems, taking into account the existing factors of global instability. It is worth noting that the increase in global turbulence objectively contributes to the consolidation processes in social entities, pushes them to overcome internal contradictions for self-preservation and maintaining the trajectory of stable social development. In this regard, social solidarity is an important value for the safe social development.

From O. Osipova's point of view, solidarity in its basic ontological dimensions is, first of all, a special state of group, corporate, collective consciousness precisely as the consciousness of unity; secondly, it is a feeling of interconnectedness with other members of the group, a feeling of "we", that is, a feeling of unity; thirdly, it is a state of people's agreement to certain common actions for the purpose of asserting their own interests. Solidarity is a unity of beliefs and actions, mutual help and support of members of a social group, which is based on common interests and the need to achieve common group goals; joint responsibility, as well as active sympathy and support for any actions or thoughts²⁷.

The importance of social solidarity as a value for the safe existence of social systems is especially enhanced in crisis situations that require cohesion, synergy of actions, and organized work for a common result from all segments of the population. For instance, G. Simmel believed that social solidarity is strengthened by conflict, which leads to social integration. Based on various historical examples, the scientist proves that conflict in society is inevitable, and one of its main forms is the conflict between the individual and society. Conflict, according to G. Simmel, does not always

²⁶ S.V. Semin, *The concept of the axiological paradigm of the fundamental principles and value principles of ensuring the national security of Ukraine*. National Institute of Strategic Studies, 2019. URL: <https://niss.gov.ua/doslidzhennya/nacionalna-bezpeka/koncept-aksiologichnoi-paradigmi-zasadnichikh-principiv-i> (access date: 09/07/2022).

²⁷ E.V. Osipova, *Mechanical and organic solidarity*. Russian sociological encyclopedia. Moscow: NORMA-INFRA, 1999, p. 476.

and does not necessarily lead to destruction, but on the contrary, it can perform important functions of preserving social relations and social systems²⁸.

In the context of our scientific research, we take into account both internal factors (positive and negative) influencing social solidarity, and external factors - the global conflict of interests, civilizational values and the struggle for spheres of influence, which under certain conditions either strengthen or weaken social integration. That is to say, the safe existence of the social system directly depends on the ability of constituent subjects to maintain a sufficient level of social solidarity to counteract internal and external factors of social instability. With that, social solidarity as a valuable basis for the safe social existence is an axiologeme that is reproduced with varying degrees of intensity - it has dynamic characteristics and needs permanent actualization at all levels of social relations.

In this sense, O. Palahniuk says, that solidarity is a phenomenon that ensures the internal unity and self-organization of society, which is manifested in its ability for social self-regulation, self-preservation and self-development, and allows the maximum use of the capabilities of all members of society for the individual and common good. Therefore, solidarity in its authentic interpretation should be understood as the self-organizing level of its consideration, which comes from internal motivation, integration of norms and practices. Nevertheless, according to theoretical ideas, all self-organizing orders (social structures) are always procedural. That is, social solidarity should be interpreted not as a static, accomplished fact, but only as a constantly dynamic process that exists only at the level of everyday interactions, which are continuously reproduced. Recently, these interactions and processes have become very rapid and significant, which is interpreted according to Z. Bauman, as "flowing modernity". That's why, solidarity is a process, a dynamic state and, at the same time, quality of society. Thus, the measure of social solidarity can be one of the main characteristics of society, which allows you to make predictions about the possible trajectory of its further development. At the same time, both strongly and weakly integrated societies get into the zone of a high level of crisis risk²⁹.

In connection with the dynamism of the phenomenon of social solidarity, possible "flash point of entropy" of various degrees in the social system and systems of a higher level, due to the risks of damage to a safe foundation, social life is not insured.

²⁸ H. Simmel, *Man as enemy*. Sociological journal, 1994, 2, p. 114-119.

²⁹ O.V. Palahniuk, *Socio-psychological aspects of social solidarity in the conditions of social transformations: an attempt at conceptualization*. Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University, 2022, 1, p. 70.

It should be noted that social solidarity as a value and a mechanism for ensuring the stable existence of the social system is the result of the reproduction of other axiologemes, in particular social justice.

Justice as a valuable aspect of society's security needs specification: clarification of the criteria for determining its level in a certain social system not only as a moral, but also a legal phenomenon, definition of "fair" and "unfair" for a given stage of the social system's existence. To assess perceptions of the level of social justice, researcher V. Studinsky suggests taking into account certain indicators:

- the degree of satisfaction of the subject (individual) with the observance of the norms of social justice at the household or everyday level;
- assessment by the subject (individual) of his participation in the process of struggle against social inequality and the effectiveness of this struggle;
- attitude to phenomena that prevent the achievement of social justice both at the level of society and at the household level;
- the degree of satisfaction of the subject (individual) with the content of work, the possibilities of influencing decision-making in the system of social or purely industrial relations, compliance with labor discipline, possibility for further education and professional level's improvement;
- the degree of determination of parameters of social justice in the system of distribution of material and moral goods, distribution of public goods;
- the degree of certainty of the criteria for the subjective assessment of the correspondence of the salary to the quantity and quality of the labor spent³⁰

Social justice is a certain compromise, a balance of interests between social groups regarding existing restrictions and advantages in the distribution of rights, freedoms, material resources, positions and statuses, opportunities to acquire symbolic capital, etc. In our opinion, social justice is determined concretely and historically, based on the indicators of the existence of a certain social system. The result of the successful implementation of social justice as a value and principle that ensures social stability is the absence of system-dangerous conflicts in it.

As emphasized in this context by L. Kravchenko: "There wasn't, isn't, and probably won't be eternal justice, suitable for all times and peoples. In the very idea of justice, as in other social ideas, in one or another combination, the past and that which does not pass, changeable and permanent appear"³¹.

³⁰ H. Simmel, *Man as enemy*. Sociological journal, 1994, 2, p. 15-16.

³¹ L.V. Kravchenko, *Justice as a choice*. Kyiv: Molod, 1998. p. 8.

Determining the essence of social justice as an axiologeme of safe existence, scientists proceed from different methodological attitudes. For instance, J. Rawls justified it by two principles: "The first requires each person is to have an equal right to the most extensive basic liberty compatible with similar liberty for others, and the second asserts that social and economic inequalities, for example, in wealth and power should be arranged so that they are both reasonably expected to be to everyone's advantage, in particular, for less successful members of society"³².

In return, the meritocratic concept of justice involves limiting the differentiation of "legitimate" and "illegitimate" inequalities and eliminating the latter by modifying the existing distribution system (distributive justice). It is not about eliminating some inequalities between people, their groups regarding certain values, benefits, services, rewards and punishments, but about legitimizing the latter by changing people's attitude towards them. Each sphere of activity has its own scale of values and priorities, its own criteria for fairness in the distribution of income, authority, its own privileges peculiar only to this sphere of activity³³.

Summarizing various approaches to understanding social justice, it is possible to single out several basic concepts derived from certain philosophical and ideological doctrines:

- egalitarianism (represented in particular by Marxism) – social justice as the equal distribution of benefits, rights, and duties among all members of society;

- liberalism – social justice is the result of self-organizing mechanisms in society with minimal state intervention;

- neoliberalism - social justice consists in maintaining a balance of interests of various social groups through active cooperation of the state and institutions of civil society;

- social-democratic approach - social justice consists in the provision by the state of high living standards for all sections of the population, as well as equal access to education, medicine, and culture through the development of a market economy and socially oriented distribution of material goods³⁴.

Therefore, social justice does not have an unambiguous interpretation in scientific concepts and social practices today. The models of its implementation can be different, but in the end they should contribute to the establishment of social harmony and peace.

³² J. Rawls, *Theory of justice*. Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk University Publishing House, 1995, p. 28.

³³ N.V. Fedina, *The concept of social justice in the theory of the state and law*. Legal novels, 2018, 4, p. 70.

³⁴ Y. Kalynovskyi, *Peculiarities of the implementation of social justice in a legal society*. Hilea: Scientific Bulletin, 2013, 74, p. 172-173.

As ukrainian scientists rightly point out, the most important indicator of the socially just orientation of society is the nature of social relations. The vector of their development can be deployed in the direction of increasing inequality, which leads to the dominance of some social groups and the subordination of others to them, and as a result - to the growth of social tension. And it can be deployed in another direction, when the decomposition of the statuses of social groups is formed and a social truce occurs, which allows social development to acquire a stable progressive character. All the mentioned characteristics reflect one or another aspect of social justice and, depending on the specifics, make it possible to judge about social progressiveness or, on the contrary, about regressiveness of society³⁵.

Apparently, the implementation of the principles of social justice is a multifaceted process in which a wide range of subjects and institutions are involved. Their activities should create conditions for increasing vectors of social development for citizens and social groups, contributing to the establishment of a balance between their interests (needs) and the state's (society's) capabilities to provide for them.

The historical experience of the existence of social systems of various types has proven that the most pluralistic and free entities in terms of the possibilities of social development of various subjects are democratic countries, which are actually, not declaratively, able to ensure the realization of democratic values, rights and freedoms of citizens. It is the development of democracy and human rights as values of social development that forms the basis for the safe functioning of social systems.

A. Kudryachenko claims that in developed democracies the entire legal system works much more effectively, and human rights violations are not systemic in nature. Values, legal and political culture, democratic regime, and civil society contribute to this. It was thanks to democracy and government support of public initiatives and non-governmental organizations that a developed and structured civil society was formed in Western European states already in the second half of the 20th century. It interacts with state structures, and the government is forced to reckon with it. These components correspond and together become effective factors of the general political atmosphere, which, in its turn, becomes a qualitative characteristic of the functioning of the state and ensures the inviolability of democratic values and, accordingly, the existing social order in the state³⁶.

³⁵ A.M. Grynenko, *Social justice as a key principle in the implementation of the social policy of the state*. Scientific works of Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University of complex "Kyiv-Mohyla Academy". Ser.: Pedagogy, 2009, 112 (99), p. 107.

³⁶ A. Kudryachenko, *Fundamental democratic values and their impact on the development of civil society in European countries*. Viche, 2015, 2. URL: <https://veche.kiev.ua/journal/4541/> (access date: 07/10/2022).

The necessity to embody democratic values as a guarantee of the stable existence of the social system is due to the fact that democracy as such contains, according to S. Kosinova:

– intrinsic value: people are seen as active participants in social processes. Democratic development enables citizens to help themselves and influence the world as a whole;

– instrumental value: democracy is more a procedure than an ideology; it is provided primarily by a set of formal rules and institutions, within which there is a place for the most diverse ideologies, and each of them is formally equal;

– creative or constructive value: democracy plays a creative role in the formation of values recognized by society. Democratic values appear in society not only through its natural development due to the various repetition of a certain model of behavior, but also through a conscious desire to implement the ideal of democracy³⁷.

In addition to thinking of the previous researcher in the context of our scientific research, we note that a developed democracy also carries social value, contributing to the economic well-being of citizens on a competitive basis and providing them with an appropriate level of social guarantees. Certainly, democratic values in combination with the implementation of the principles of the social state acquire special stabilizing significance for the existence of social systems in periods of crisis. Strengthening the social protection of citizens in democratic social systems is an important guarantee of counteracting the negative consequences of global turbulence.

Nowadays, the concept of the welfare state includes not only the obligations to introduce and effectively manage the social security system, but also to effectively redistribute public goods. The notion of social welfare, on which the principle of the welfare state is based, is to ensure that no one has to live in poverty and to avoid significant inequality in the distribution of public goods. Although the question of whether the principle of the welfare state establishes positive obligations to provide certain benefits to all its citizens or only gives the state such a right is not yet definitively determined. For instance, most representatives of the German constitutional doctrine believe that the state has a constitutional duty to guarantee a minimum standard of living for all its citizens. As the Federal Constitutional Court of Germany (Bundesverfassungsgericht) pointed out, "human dignity is at the top of the value order of the Basic Law"³⁸.

³⁷ S. Kosinov, *Democratic principles and values in the organization of public power*. Bulletin of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, 2013, 3 (74), p. 129-132.

³⁸ T.P. Popovych, *Legal model of a modern democratic state*. Comparative and analytical law, 2016, 1, p. 67.

It is quite obvious that the implementation of democratic values in social entities that strive for stable functioning should be complemented by an effective system of social protection of citizens.

As an interim conclusion, we emphasize that democracy in itself is an important value for the progressive development of humanity. Without idealizing democracy, but understanding its merits and demerits, we would agree with the opinion of A. Sen that democracy is a set of values, in particular, first, political freedom is an element of human freedom in general, the realization of civil and political rights as a crucial condition for the good life of individuals as social beings. Participation in social and political life has a self-sufficient value for human life and well-being. Secondly, democracy has an important ancillary value, increasing the chances of people to express and defend their claims to political attention (especially in terms of satisfying their economic needs). Thirdly, the practice of democracy gives citizens a chance to learn from each other, helps society form its values and priorities. Even the idea of "needs", namely the understanding of "economic needs", requires public discussion and exchange of information, views... In this meaning, democracy has a constructive value in addition to its self-sufficient value for the lives of citizens and its auxiliary value in making political decisions³⁹.

The strength of democracy, which should contribute to the strengthening of social stability in conditions of global turbulence, is the comprehensive implementation of human rights and freedoms. Accordingly, the social system that is capable of truly embodying the democratic rights and freedoms of citizens, making them effective participants in political-legal and socio-economic processes, becomes more competitive and safer in the world. Only an active, patriotic and free citizen can effectively and consciously oppose destabilizing factors of both internal and external nature. In this sense, T. Slinko and O. Uvarov emphasize that freedom of expression is one of the prerequisites for the formation and existence of a democratic society, it belongs to universal human values of primary importance, as it allows not only to freely express one's own views, but also to reveal the potential of the individual⁴⁰.

From V. Sokurenko's point of view, one of the properties of human rights is their ability to be considered a universal value. That is to say they are important for any civil society, regardless of the national and cultural context. The issue of the existing international documents on the

³⁹ A. Sen, *Democracy as a universal value* / Democracy: an anthology. Arrange O. Protsenko Kyiv: Smoloskip, 2005, p. 126.

⁴⁰ T. Slinko, & O. Uvarova, *Freedom of expression in ukraine: (non)sustainable constitutional tradition*. Baltic Journal of European Studies, 2019, 9(3), p. 26. doi:10.1515/bjes-2019-0020

formulation of the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen is quite controversial, since in the case of the development of such generalizing legal provisions, questions inevitably arise as to which theory of rights to proceed from and which standards in this area to consider as a model. However, the complexities of the law-making process do not exclude the idea of possible use of human rights as a value common for the all world. First of all, their universality is manifested in the fact that it expresses interests that an individual cannot renounce - life, freedom, property, honor, etc. Moreover, the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen are a means of protection against state intervention in certain spheres of social relations and, accordingly, a means of realizing the freedom of individuals. At the same time, they provide an opportunity for citizens to influence state management (for example, voting rights) and make political decisions (in civil society, its members and public institutions are involved in the process of discussing such decisions through appropriate mechanisms). It should also be added that human rights are the basis for mutual understanding and interaction between representatives of different cultures, and this also shows their universality. Since human rights involve treating everyone as a bearer of such rights, they ensure the perception of another subject of relations as equal. Therefore, they exclude the theory of "subhuman", treating other members of society only as a means of realizing one's own interests. That is to say, in civil society, a person's belonging to another social or ethnic group, professing other views and beliefs cannot be grounds for disrespecting him⁴¹.

The implementation of human rights and freedoms in the social space of modern democracies promotes self-organization and self-development of citizens, allows them to realize their involvement and responsibility in relation to national processes, in particular in the field of security. In the institutional dimension, in the context of our research, we have to talk about the human right to security, which involves both external and internal aspects.

From the point of view of V. Tykhyi, human security lies in the rule of human rights and freedoms. The following means are used to ensure it:

1) the state and society contribute to the creation of conditions necessary for the full and unhindered realization of human rights and freedoms;

2) human rights and freedoms are the limit of state intervention in human life;

⁴¹ V.V. Sokurenko, *Human rights as a fundamental value*. National and international mechanisms for the protection of human rights: theses add. All-Ukrainian round table (Kharkiv, April 20 2016) / Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, Kharkiv. national University of Internal Affairs Kharkiv: Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, 2016, p. 8-9.

3) measures for the protection of rights and freedoms, legal rules regarding human security are foreseen, in particular, natural human rights and their guarantees, prohibitions and limitations of groundless interference of the state and its organs in human life, means of self-defense of a person against encroachments on human rights and freedoms by both the state and private individuals, are enshrined in the Constitution and laws, other measures to prevent and exclude violations of human rights and freedoms;

4) in case of violation of human rights and freedoms, activities are carried out and measures are taken for the direct protection of human rights and freedoms - termination of violation (threat of violation) of human rights and freedoms, their restoration, elimination of the consequences of committed offenses, bringing the guilty to legal responsibility, compensation for material and moral damage caused by such violations, realization of legal responsibility⁴².

From our point of view, the influence of various values on the stability of the social order, on the one hand, has a complex nature, and on the other hand, in certain periods of society's existence, certain values become paramount (for example, the value of peace in ukrainian society nowadays).

Analyzing comprehensively the issue of the value basis of the safe existence of social systems in conditions of global turbulence, ukrainian scientists draw attention to the following generalizing points. Firstly, values as a social phenomenon constitute a spiritual and cultural basis for the safe functioning of social systems. Despite the importance of various values, the collective values that determine the social behavior of broad sections of the population acquire special importance for the stable existence of society. Secondly, for the vital activity of democratic social systems, the system-forming factor (value) is law (human rights), since this value constitutes the existence of other axiologemes for the safe development of society, such as freedom, responsibility, justice, solidarity. Thirdly, the security of the functioning of democratic social systems is determined both by the general development of the political and legal and civil culture of society, and by the rooting of civic values in the worldview of individual subjects of the social space, especially those endowed with power⁴³.

Conclusions

Summarizing the above, we note that the value guidelines for the safe existence of society in the conditions of intensification of global instability

⁴² V.P. Tikhyy, *Human security is the main object of Ukraine's national security. Spirituality of Person: methodology, theory and practice*, 2017, 4, p. 326.

⁴³ *National security: worldview and theoretical and methodological foundations: monograph* / by general ed. O. P. Dzoban. Kharkiv: Pravo, 2021, p. 347.

are a component of the national and international security system. Values are directly the core of spiritual and informational security of any social system. The transformation of global and regional security configurations requires adequate changes in the strategy and tactical steps of the institutional subjects of ensuring national security regarding the leveling of new risks and challenges to social stability. Today, experts use several methods to determine the stability of social systems, which are constantly being improved.

A system-forming component of the safe existence of social organisms is a complex of values and axiological priorities that correspond to the cultural, mental and spiritual background of a particular people. We do believe that solidarity at all levels of society is an important value imperative for a stable social existence. Social solidarity ensures both internal and external stability of society due to constantly reproduced social ties, actualization of various interests of the subjects of activity, strengthening of their worldview and spiritual unity, etc.

In order to strengthen the stability of society in the face of global challenges, the principles of justice of the democratic type must be reproduced in the social system and human rights and freedoms must be implemented in practice. To counteract external threats and internal factors of instability, democratic social systems must demonstrate flexibility in decision-making, ensure socio-economic growth of the population, take care of the balance of interests of social groups, promote the development of science and education, etc.

References:

Bauman, Z., *Postmodern ethics* (2006) / Trans. from English R. Zimovets, O. Yudin, D. Korol. Kyiv: Port-Royal, 329 p.

Danilyan, O.G., Dzeban, O.P., Kalynovskyi, Y.Y., (2022), *Social instability as a global trend of the modern world*. *Cogito*, Vol. 14, Iss. 3, p. 141-162.

Fedina, N.V., (2018), *The concept of social justice in the theory of the state and law*. *Legal novels*, 4, p. 66-72.

Getman, A.P., Danilyan, O.G., Dzeban, A.P., Kalynovskyi, Y.Y., (2022), *Modern ontology: reflection on the continuity of cyberspace and virtual reality*. *Revista de Filosofía*, Vol. 39, Iss. 102, p. 78-94.

Grynenko, A.M., (2009), *Social justice as a key principle in the implementation of the social policy of the state*. Scientific works of Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University of complex "Kyiv-Mohyla Academy". Ser.: Pedagogy, 112 (99), p. 104-107.

- Hegel, W.V.G., (2004), *Phenomenology of spirit* / trans. with Germ. P. Taraschuk, science. ed. trans. Y. Kushakov. Kyiv: Osnovy, 548 p.
- Kalashnikova, L.V., (2016), *Socio-philosophical origins of the formation of the concept of security in protosociology*. Grani, 9. p. 6-13.
- Kalynovskyi, Y., (2013), *Peculiarities of the implementation of social justice in a legal society*. Hilea: Scientific Bulletin, 74, p. 172-175.
- Kosinov, S., (2013), *Democratic principles and values in the organization of public power*. Bulletin of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, 3 (74), p. 128-134.
- Kravchenko, L.V., (1998), *Justice as a choice*. Kyiv: Molod, 256 p.
- Kudryachenko, A., (2015), *Fundamental democratic values and their impact on the development of civil society in European countries*. Viche, 2. Available at: <https://veche.kiev.ua/journal/4541/>
- Kysil, Y., (2009), *Principles of social security formation in multicultural societies*. Political management, 2, p. 128-135.
- Meliakova, Y., Kovalenko, I., Kalnytskyi, E., Kovalenko, H., (2021), *Performativity and self-exploitation: body significance in late capitalist era*. Cogito, Vol. 13, Iss. 4, p. 7-29.
- Montesquieu, C.-L., (1999), *On the spirit of laws*. Moscow: Thought, 674 p.
- National security: worldview and theoretical and methodological foundations: monograph* (2021) / by general ed. Dzoban O. P., Kharkiv: Pravo, 776 p.
- Osipova, E.V., (1999), *Mechanical and organic solidarity*. Russian sociological encyclopedia. Moscow: NORMA-INFRA, 672 p.
- Palahniuk, O.V., (2022), *Socio-psychological aspects of social solidarity in the conditions of social transformations: an attempt at conceptualization*. Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University, 1, p. 67-76.
- Petryshyn, O.V., & Hyliaka, O.S., (2021), *Human rights in the digital age: Challenges, threats and prospects*. Journal of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, 28(1), p. 15-23. doi:10.37635/jnalsu.28(1).2021.15-23
- Pivovarov, V., Drachuk, S., (2007), *Philosophical problems of security as a methodological basis for ensuring the security of the stock market*. Legal informatics, 2(14), p. 77-82.
- Popovych, T.P., (2016), *Legal model of a modern democratic state*. Comparative and analytical law, 1, p. 65-68.
- Rawls, J., (1995), *Theory of justice*. Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk University Publishing House, 511 p.
- Semin, S.V., (2016), *The concept of the axiological paradigm of the fundamental principles and value principles of ensuring the national security of Ukraine*. National Institute of Strategic Studies. Available at:

<https://niss.gov.ua/doslidzhennya/nacionalna-bezpeka/koncept-aksiologichnoi-paradigmi-zasadnichikh-principiv-i>.

Sen, A., (2005), *Democracy as a universal value* / Democracy: an anthology. Arrange O. Protsenko Kyiv: Smoloskip, p. 120-132.

Simmel, H., (1994), *Man as enemy*. Sociological journal, 2, p. 114-119.

Slinko, T., & Uvarova, O., (2019), *Freedom of expression in ukraine: (non)sustainable constitutional tradition*. Baltic Journal of European Studies, 9(3), p. 25-42. doi:10.1515/bjes-2019-0020

Sokurenko, V.V., (2016), *Human rights as a fundamental value*. National and international mechanisms for the protection of human rights: theses add. All-Ukrainian round table (m. Kharkiv, April 20 2016) / Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, Kharkiv. national University of Internal Affairs affairs Kharkiv: Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs, p. 7-9.

Studinsky, V., (2009), *The issue of social justice in the context of social policy*. Ukraine: aspects of Labor, 1, p. 13-16.

Tikhiy, V.P., (2017), *Human security is the main object of Ukraine's national security*. Spirituality of Person: methodology, theory and practice, 4, p. 323-329.